

The price of actor diversity: Measuring project developers' willingness to accept risks in renewable energy auctions

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ABSTRACT

Renewable energy (RE) auctions were partly introduced to lower the cost of policy support. However, policy-makers are increasingly aware that effective policies require a broader set of objectives that include securing actor diversity and social acceptance. While several countries have introduced measures to incentivize citizen participation in RE projects to meet those objectives, little is known about their effect on the risk perceptions of developers in auction settings. Based on insights from 559 experimental choices made by 61 European project developers, this study investigates risk-return preferences for different onshore wind energy auction designs. We show that developers are willing to accept the requirement to submit bid bonds up to a certain threshold, and that a 36-month realisation period is preferred overall. While developers may be open to citizen co-investment, the risk premiums they require increase with the share of capital offered to local residents in auction settings, highlighting an apparent trade-off between promoting actor diversity and low-cost RE deployment. Policymakers unwilling to compensate developers for the price of increasing actor diversity may have to find other ways to promote citizen participation in order to achieve RE objectives, as this factor may have important implications for the acceptance of RE deployment.

1. Introduction

To foster the deployment of renewable energy (RE) at the lowest possible cost to taxpayers and energy consumers, the European Commission proposed in 2014 a shift from administratively-set support schemes to competitive tendering (EC, 2019, 2014). Since then, auctions have become the dominant instrument for allocating financial support to RE projects across the European Union (EU) (CEER, 2020). Auctions introduce new risks for project developers and have been shown to create disproportional challenges for smaller actors such as RE communities (Grashof, 2019; Morris, 2019; Tews, 2018). Further, RE projects – in particular, onshore wind – are also facing growing opposition in many countries, which often results in additional risks and delays for developers (Brindley and Fraile, 2021; IEA, 2020; Quentin, 2019). In

this context, the European Commission called for a more proactive role of citizens in decarbonization efforts to foster the acceptance and deployment of RE infrastructure (EC, 2015). This has become even more relevant in light of recent renewed ambition to engage in climate action.¹

Research shows that citizen participation plays an important role in fostering the acceptance of RE projects (Bauwens and Devine-Wright, 2018; De Luca et al., 2020; Hvelplund et al., 2017; Vuichard et al., 2019), including financial participation through citizen investment (Johansen and Emborg, 2018; Lienhoop, 2018; Musall and Kuik, 2011; Warren and McFadyen, 2010). However, projects with shared ownership – i.e., RE assets jointly owned by professional developers and local citizens through, for example, co-investment schemes – may be associated with increased risk and costs for developers (Goedkoop and

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¹ In April 2021, the European Parliament and Council of Europe reached partial agreement on increasing the stringency of the 2030 target for greenhouse gases emission reductions from a 40% to a 55% reduction (European Parliament, 2021). This has led to an upward revision of the EU's current 32% RES target to at least a 40% RES share in final energy use by 2030, which itself would require a threefold increase in the 179 GW of wind power capacity installed today (EC, 2021, 2020; WindEurope, 2021). The European Commission expects Member States to use RE auctions to operationalise more predictable RE power capacity deployments, both in terms of support cost (competitiveness) and pace (timeliness) (EC, 2020; European Parliament and Council of Europe, 2018).

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Devine-Wright, 2016). In an effort to increase citizen engagement and local acceptance, EU legislation mandates that Member States introduce provisions aimed at enabling citizen participation in RE projects through a variety of measures, including community-based co-investment and joint ownership models (European Parliament and Council of Europe, 2019, 2018). The European Commission also plans to periodically assess the performance of national RE auction schemes to ensure their suitability according to several criteria – namely, cost-effectiveness, actor diversity, and local acceptance of RE infrastructure (European Parliament and Council of Europe, 2018).

Auction designs vary across countries (del Río and Kiefer, 2021), and can be tailored to meet different policy objectives (Mora et al., 2017a). Until now, only a few EU Member States have introduced specific auction design elements to incentivize citizen participation (BMW, 2017; CRE, 2020; DECC, 2020a). Their experience exemplifies how tailoring auctions to ensure actor diversity remains a challenging endeavour (Mora et al., 2017a). Indeed, these measures have typically resulted in a low share of successful bids that included citizen participation (Gsänger and Karl, 2020; Rüdinger, 2019), suggesting a limited understanding of bidders' risk perceptions. To fill this gap, our study addresses the following research question:

How do different auction design elements aimed at fostering citizen participation influence the risk perceptions of RE project developers, and their willingness to participate in auctions?

Our study addresses this question by drawing on insights from a choice experiment conducted with 61 European onshore wind energy project developers who made a total of 559 experimental decisions. The objective was to investigate the risk perceptions of developers with regard to various actor-specific auction design elements and shed light on their preferences for different forms of citizen participation. In doing so, this study contributes to research on RE auctions, citizen participation, and investor decision-making. In particular, it contributes to the growing academic and policy debate about how actor diversity can be fostered in the context of RE auctions (Álvarez and del Río, 2022; Grashof, 2019), and to the discussion about policies aimed at mandating citizen co-investment (Goedkoop and Devine-Wright, 2016; Rüdinger, 2019). Gaining a better understanding of how auction design elements influence the risk perceptions of project developers allows us to derive evidence-based policy recommendations that may help policymakers to find the right balance between cost-reducing and risk-increasing auction designs.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews key auction-related risks and existing actor-diversity measures introduced in RE auction settings. Section 3 elaborates on the methodological approach and experimental design. Section 4 reports and discusses the results of the choice experiment. Section 5 concludes by summarizing key findings, discussing policy implications, and suggesting future lines of research.

2. Background and literature review

The introduction of RE auctions was triggered by a perception that previous support schemes may have been overly generous to some RE producers, while simultaneously becoming increasingly costly for electricity end-users (Gründinger, 2017; Vorholz, 2012). As the cost of RE support is ultimately borne by consumers, policymakers are concerned about the cost-effectiveness of support schemes, and would like to avoid situations where investors capture higher profits than needed to achieve energy targets. Previous research on RE policymaking has shown that perceived risk is an important moderator of policy effectiveness, and that attempts at reducing policy cost may come with increases in risk (Lüthi and Wüstenhagen, 2012). Since investors do not only look at returns, but at risk-adjusted returns, policies aimed at maximizing cost-effectiveness may unintentionally crowd out investors who perceive the return of a policy scheme as being too low to compensate for the risk. This could result in (a) a lack of actor diversity, meaning

only those investors with the lowest return expectations and/or the greatest ability to absorb risk remain, or even (b), a failure to reach policy targets if the remaining investors are unable to mobilize sufficient capital (Karneyeva and Wüstenhagen, 2017). Both effects are counterproductive for effective long-term policies. In the case of actor diversity, there are concerns that a negative feedback loop could occur if small, local developers are crowded out, potentially accentuating social acceptance challenges. Therefore, policymakers would be well advised to not just monitor the short-term cost-effectiveness of policies, but to keep an eye on investors' risk perceptions and the required risk-adjusted returns of different investor types, including those who take on board citizen co-investment.

As with other RE policies, it is the specific design elements of auctions that determine the risk-return expectations of investors. To understand how auction design elements influence risk perceptions, this section first reviews salient auction-related risks and their impact on different types of bidders. It also provides examples of actor-specific measures introduced in some European auction schemes to mitigate these risks and promote actor diversity. In doing so, it lays the foundations for the following analysis and discussion.

2.1. Overview of risks to project developers in renewable energy auctions

Several auction design elements have the potential to influence risks and returns for investors (Polzin et al., 2019; Winkler et al., 2018). Auction-related risks vary at different project development stages, and their impact depends on bidders' size, financial robustness, and business model (Đukan et al., 2019). This section provides an overview of how allocation, planning, qualification, non-compliance, and shared ownership risks may affect larger and smaller bidders. These risks represent key considerations in the decisions of developers to participate in RE auctions, and have in most cases been targeted by policy measures aimed at promoting actor diversity in auction settings (see Subsection 2.2 and 3.3). They are thus operationalized in the subsequent choice experiment through the inclusion of different levels of competition, bid bonds, realisation periods, and citizen co-investment requirements. Beyond this, auction design elements that may also affect exposure to other risks are specified as constants in the choice experiment to avoid dominant effects, enabling a focus on specific actor-diversity measures. These include, for example, the type of remuneration schemes which influence exposure to price risk, and the choice of pricing rule which may induce strategic bidding and increase the risk of project non-realisation (Polzin et al., 2019).² Fig. 1 summarizes the conceptual framework used in this study.

2.1.1. Allocation risk

The risk of (not) obtaining support – i.e., allocation risk – is the largest source of risk introduced by auction-based support schemes (Đukan and Kitzing, 2021). As such, auctions create structures whereby developers invest resources into projects while remaining uncertain of their financial viability until results are announced (Botta, 2019). Since larger bidders are usually more financially robust than smaller developers, they are less exposed to allocation risk. They tend to develop large project portfolios and benefit from several revenue streams, thus diversifying the risk of sunk costs that project failures may incur (Đukan et al., 2019).

In contrast, smaller developers who operate locally – particularly citizen-led organisations – may follow a “one-project approach” (Lucas et al., 2017). As such, their relative exposure to sunk costs is greater. Further, they may face local constraints like limited space or wind

² The remuneration scheme determines the payment mechanism a public entity provides to financially support successful bids, while the pricing rule defines the mechanism of selecting winning bidders and awarding support to them (AURES, 2019a; 2019b).

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of major risks associated with different auction design elements, their appearance in the project development process, and their duration. The black boxes represent the auction design elements that are considered within the scope of this study, while the grey boxes represent the elements that are outside of its scope. The list of auction design elements is not exhaustive.

resources, which may hinder resource-optimization. Smaller actors tend to have higher capital expenditure due to their limited capacity to benefit from economies of scale (Grashof, 2019). Additionally, citizen-led organisations are also not exclusively profit-driven but instead emphasize principles like procedural and distributional fairness, environmental stewardship, and community empowerment (Fischer et al., 2021; Holstenkamp and Kahla, 2016; Seyfang et al., 2013; Yildiz et al., 2015). These characteristics can result in relatively high costs, which may be offset by lower return requirements, or decrease price competitiveness and increase exposure to allocation risk. Beyond these actor-specific characteristics, allocation risk is also amplified by exposure to other types of risk; in particular, planning, qualification, non-compliance, and shared ownership risks.

2.1.2. Planning risk

Auctions are volume-based support allocation mechanisms (Held et al., 2014) in which an authority defines the volumes of a good to be auctioned and plans an auction schedule accordingly. Defining and communicating such RE support rollout provides clarity to investors about future market demand (Gephart et al., 2017). Organising long-term, continuous auction schedules increases certainty compared to short-term “stop-and-go” schedules (Mora et al., 2017; Wigand et al., 2016), and reduces planning risk – a risk caused by auction volumes and frequency and their effects on project development uncertainty.

Planning risk is closely linked to allocation risk, mainly because auction volumes also affect the level of competition – i.e., the ratio between the expected volume of power capacity submitted by auction participants and the volume of power capacity tendered by the authority conducting the auction (the auctioneer). Setting auction volumes at levels at which the auctioned RE capacity is relatively scarce compared to the potential volume of the submitted projects may increase the level

of competition and reduce support costs (del Río, 2017; del Río and Linares, 2014; Winkler et al., 2018). While this increases allocation risk, it also affects planning risk, as project developers have less clarity in their ability to recuperate development costs. This can particularly affect smaller actors who develop small-scale and less cost-efficient projects. In contrast, larger developers who operate internationally and who seek sites with greater resources can tap into multiple markets. This increases their relative competitiveness and reduces their exposure to planning risk.

2.1.3. Qualification risk

When preparing for an auction, bidders often have to meet material and financial qualification requirements – e.g., by securing building permits or submitting financial guarantees (Soysal and Kurgpold, 2016). In the latter case, developers must submit bid bonds to qualify for auction participation, and/or performance bonds to ensure timely project realisation. Such requirements may decrease the short-term financial liquidity of bidders, especially when balance sheets are small relative to the size of guarantees required (Đukan et al., 2019). As such, they may constitute a barrier to auction participation for capital-constrained actors (Held et al., 2014; IRENA and CEM, 2015; Wigand et al., 2016) – in particular, for smaller developers or community-led organisations (Botta, 2019).

2.1.4. Non-compliance risk

Auctioneers implement penalties by retaining financial guarantees when bidders fail to comply with contractual agreements – e.g., if projects are not realized within a specific timeframe (Soysal and Kurgpold, 2016). Shorter realisation periods may increase non-compliance risk – i.e., the risk of incurring penalties in the case of non-compliance with the requirements defined in the awarded support contract (Hochberg and

Poudineh, 2018; IRENA and CEM, 2015). Smaller and less experienced developers have less expertise dealing with pitfalls during the permitting process (Amazo et al., 2020). This makes them more vulnerable to breaching realisation deadlines than their larger counterparts if permits are procured after auctions. As described in Subsection 2.1.1, smaller actors also have less ability to spread the cost of paying penalties due to the limited size of their project portfolios. In contrast, longer realisation periods could reduce their exposure to non-compliance risk. However, it could also stimulate underbidding and speculative behaviours by allowing bidders to postpone their final investment decisions to when the actual costs and benefits of developing a project become clearer (del Ro and Linares, 2014; Matthus et al., 2021).

2.1.5. Shared ownership risk

Auctioneers can introduce different auction design elements to foster citizen co-investment (del Ro, 2017; Lundberg, 2019). However, promoting (or even mandating) shared ownership can pose several challenges to developers. While co-investments might enable developers to mitigate the risk of public contestation – thereby increasing the likelihood of securing building permits (Goedkoop and Devine-Wright, 2016; Slee, 2015) –, trust plays a central role in the success of such arrangements (Kalkbrenner and Roosen, 2016). Locally embedded developers who share local values might have an advantage over external developers who would need to allocate substantial resources to locate, mobilize, and entrust local citizens (Goedkoop and Devine-Wright, 2016). Larger external developers may thus be more exposed to the risk of failed co-ownership than smaller actors. Local constraints such as population density, average income, and project concentration may also limit the amount of citizen capital available (FPF, 2017). This could challenge the realisation of shared ownership initiatives and increase bidders' exposure to financial and non-compliance risks. Other aspects of co-investment schemes like the method used to determine the price of shares or the minimum holding period can also influence exposure to shared ownership risk for developers.

2.2. Auction design elements to mitigate risks and promote actor diversity

To inform the design of our choice experiment, this subsection provides an overview of how some European countries have implemented auction design elements to address the risks presented in Subsection 2.1 and promote actor diversity. While several EU Member States have introduced specific actor diversity measures, the overview presented here provides details on the German, French, and Irish experiences. To the authors' knowledge, only these three countries had implemented design elements calibrated to induce greater actor diversity in their national auction schemes at the time of writing. These cases are also of particular interest as they illustrate contrasting approaches in terms of policy measures, timing, duration, and experiences yielded thus far for incentivising greater citizen participation. A brief overview of these design elements and their outcomes are reviewed and summarised in Table 1.

2.2.1. Financial qualification

To decrease qualification and allocation risks, auctioneers can calibrate financial guarantees to different actor types. For instance, both Germany and France introduced a 30,000 €/MW bid bond requirement in their onshore wind energy auctions (see Table 1). While France maintained the same requirement for all auction participants, Germany initially differentiated between actor groups by imposing a 15,000 €/MW bid bond on 'community energy companies' (CECs). However, the auctioneer withdrew this preferential rule in 2018, and instead applied a uniform bid bond of 30,000 €/MW for all bidders. Similarly, Ireland's first RE auction required a 2,000 €/MW bid bond and a 25,000

€/MW performance bond from all participants, except for some community-led projects.

2.2.2. Realisation period

To reduce non-compliance risk, auctioneers can also differentiate between different actor-specific realisation periods. For instance, France and Ireland imposed a 36-month and 23-month realisation period, respectively, for all auction participants (see Table 1). In contrast, Germany initially imposed a 30-month realisation period for commercial developers, and 54 months for CECs. However, the auctioneer rescinded this preferential condition in 2018 and imposed a 30-month realisation period for all auction participants.

2.2.3. Shared ownership

In 2017, Germany introduced preferential conditions for projects with citizen ownership, including less stringent material and financial pre-qualification requirements, a longer realisation period, and actor-specific pricing rules (BMW, 2017). However, all preferential conditions were withdrawn in 2018, except for the pricing rule. In tandem with Federal provisions, the state of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern also introduced a law obliging project developers to offer local residents and municipalities the possibility to invest in projects and own at least 20% of shares in project companies, irrespective of their participation in auctions (GVOBl. M-V S. 258, 2016).

In France, successful bidders received a 3 €/MWh premium if local actors owned at least 40% of the joint-stock company or cooperative shares (with voting rights), and a 1 €/MWh premium if at least 10% of the project value was financed locally via equity or debt investment (CRE, 2020).³ These measures are being reviewed and may be replaced by a multi-criteria, points-based ranking system whereby additional points can be granted to bids that pledge to include citizen investment (nergie Partage, 2020; Pi, 2021).

Finally, Ireland's first auction established a separate actor-specific category for projects with shared ownership (i.e., community-led projects),⁴ along with two technology-driven categories. While community-led projects could bid in any category, if they competed only in the 'community' category, they benefited from pre-qualification exemptions (DECC, 2020a). However, in the next Irish auction the 'community' category will be reserved for projects that are fully owned by local communities, and a separate citizen investment scheme could be introduced (DECC, 2021a; 2021b).

2.2.4. Auction outcomes: level of competition and citizen participation

In Germany, while the first three onshore wind auctions in 2017 appear to have resulted in a high number of citizen-led projects, a high level of competition, and low average awarded support prices (Lundberg, 2019), the level of competition has decreased and remained low since the withdrawal of preferential conditions for CECs in 2018 (see Table 1). These conditions were terminated due to their alleged misuse by some developers, who maneuvered around legal definitions to benefit from preferential treatment when in fact their financial and operational structures were not representative of CECs (Gsnger and Karl, 2020). This resulted in the crowding out of community initiatives and a steep decline of citizen-driven projects (Gsnger and Karl, 2020; Sach et al., 2029). Since 2018, average awarded prices have remained high and competition levels low.

The French experience showcases a contrasting outcome, with only one undersubscribed onshore wind energy auction round. Relatively high levels of competition have been paired with declining support costs

³ This included co-investments involving at least 20 individuals, or local authorities (i.e., municipalities).

⁴ "Community-led projects" corresponded to projects at least 51% owned by a Renewable Energy Community, and where at least 51% of all profits, dividends, and surpluses thereby derived were returned to this entity (DECC, 2020a,b).

Table 1

Overview of onshore wind auction design elements for inducing citizen participation in the German, French, and Irish auction schemes, and their outcomes.

	Germany	France	Ireland
Auction design elements			
Financial qualification	- 30,000 €/MW bid bond (2017 only: 15,000 €/MW for citizen energy companies (CECs))	- 30,000 €/MW bid bond	- 2,000 €/MW bid bond and 25,000 €/MW performance bond for all bidders, except some 'community-led projects' (2020 round); 7 €/MWh bid bond and 24 €/MWh performance bond (2022 round)
Realisation period	- 30 months (2017 only: 54 months for CECs)	- 36 months	- 23 months
Citizen participation	- 2017: preferential rules for CECs (i.e., lower bid bond, no material pre-qualification, longer realisation period, and 'uniform pricing') - 2018: preferential rules suspended, except 'uniform pricing' - 2021: new voluntary payments to local municipalities scheme, operating outside tenders	- 2017: bidders offering capital shares to local residents benefit from additional premiums - 2018: 'crowdfunding' and 'participatory investment' modalities are specified - Today, 'participatory premium' under review, to substitute by points-based ranking system (95% of points for price, 5% for citizen participation)	- Preference category for 'Community-led Projects' (separate from developer-led projects) - 'Community category' projects exempt from financial and performance guarantees, and independent pricing assessment - Contribution to community benefit fund for all bidders, irrespective of category
Auction outcomes			
Level of competition & actor diversity	- In 2017, CECs represented 71%, 84%, and 89% of total capacity bided in each round, respectively. Capacity oversubscription (2.67 kW, 2.93 kW, and 2.59 kW offered per kW tendered, respectively), paired with cost reductions (avg. clearing price 5.78 €/ct./kWh, 4.29 €/ct./kWh, and 3.82 €/ct./kWh, respectively) - Since 2018, 60% of all rounds undersubscribed (0.8 kW avg. capacity offered per kW tendered). Low competition is insufficient to reduce costs (avg. strike prices between 5.9 and 6.3 €/ct./kWh)	- All auction rounds but one have been oversubscribed (1.7 kW of avg. power capacity offered per kW tendered); support cost reductions (6.59 €/ct./kWh strike price in first 2017 round, 5.97 €/ct./kWh in 2020 round) - Weak citizen involvement: 2017 auction results included 32% of awarded projects pledging citizen financial participation; no awarded bidder opted for citizen co-investment in 2018 round	- 1st auction (2020) undersubscribed (0.85 MWh of capacity bided per MWh tendered) - Low level of competition, with an avg. strike price of 10.4 €/ct./kWh for the 'community' preference category and 7.4 €/ct./kWh for the remaining 'conventional' projects awarded – compared to a ceiling price of €/ct.12/kWh

Source: Authors' elaboration based on BGBl (2020), BMWi (2017), Bundesnetzagentur (2017a, 2017b, 2017c), CRE (2020, 2018a, 2018b, 2017), DECC (2021a, 2021b, 2020a, 2020b), Eirgrid (2020), Énergie Partagée (2020), Pié (2021).

(see Table 1); this arguably occurring at the expense of a decline in citizen participation (Rüdinger, 2019). Finally, Ireland's first auction yielded a low level of competition, while fewer than 10% of awarded projects were community-led (Eirgrid, 2020).

3. Methodology

3.1. Methodological approach

This study uses a choice experiment to investigate the influence of key auction design elements on the decision of onshore wind energy project developers to participate in auctions, and to estimate their willingness-to-accept distinct auction-related risks. Choice experiments are rooted in discrete choice and random utility theory (Manski, 1977; McFadden, 1974), and have been widely used by scholars to elucidate the preferences of investors for clean energy investment (Petrovich et al., 2021; Salm and Wüstenhagen, 2018; Hille et al., 2018; Kubli et al., 2018; Salm et al., 2016; Menyeh, 2021). This approach assumes that objects can be decomposed into sets of attributes and attribute levels, and that each level is associated with a part-worth utility.⁵ It also assumes that individuals aim to maximize the overall utility obtained from aggregating attribute-specific part-worth utilities (Lancaster, 1966; McFadden, 1980). Since preferences are investigated based on attributes and levels that are experimentally manipulated, researchers can elicit stated preferences for concepts beyond those observable on existing markets (Holmes et al., 2017; Louviere et al., 2000). This strategy is particularly suitable in this context as the historical data on citizen participation in RE auctions that is required to apply

⁵ Part-worth utilities are understood here as the levels of utility individuals impute to specific characteristics of objects (or attribute levels). The overall utility of an object corresponds thus to the sum of its part-worth utilities.

revealed-preference methods is limited. Choice experiments have also been applied to examine the effect policies have on investment decisions (Melliger and Lilliestam, 2021; Chassot et al., 2014; Lüthi and Wüstenhagen, 2012; Pons-Seres de Brauwert and Cohen, 2020), including in RE auction settings (Botta, 2019).

3.2. Survey structure

The questionnaire was created using Sawtooth Software's module SSI⁶ and included four sections. First, respondents were asked a set of questions about their prior experience with RE auctions and factors influencing their bidding decisions. Second, they were introduced to the choice experiment and assigned a series of randomized choice tasks designed to elicit their preferences for hypothetical auction designs. Third, respondents were asked a set of questions aimed at investigating their experience with citizen participation and preferences for related support measures. Fourth, we collected socio-economic data about respondents (see Table A1 in appendix). The survey was pretested with experts between February and April 2021 and improved based on their feedback prior to the start of the data collection.

3.3. Choice experiment design

The choice experiment comprised two parts. First, respondents were asked to imagine that they were planning to participate in a hypothetical auction hosted by a European country with a robust credit rating and comprehensive regulatory framework to obtain support for an onshore wind energy project. The introductory text provided a thorough description of the hypothetical auction scheme and project characteristics (see Fig. A1 in appendix). Second, respondents were presented

⁶ <https://sawtoothsoftware.com>.

Table 2
Attributes and attribute levels manipulated in the choice experiment.

Attributes	Description	Attribute levels
Gross IRR	The expected annual financial return on investment before fees and taxes if the project is awarded support in the auction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4% • 7% • 10%
Financial pre-qualification	The financial guarantee required to be able to participate in the auction. The guarantee is kept by the auctioning authority if the bid is successful at the auction, but the project is not realized.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5,000 €/MW • 30,000 €/MW • 70,000 €/MW
Mandatory share offer to local residents	The obligation to offer all citizens who have their permanent address within a 5 km radius of the project the opportunity to invest equity capital and own a minimum share (%) of the project with voting rights.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0% • 10% • 20%
Level of competition	The level of competition expected in the auction round. Defined as a function of the volume of power capacity tendered by the auctioning authority and expected aggregated volume of power capacity auction participants submitted in their bids to obtain support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level of competition • Medium level of competition • High level of competition
Realisation period	The amount of time successful bidders are granted to develop the project after winning the auction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24 months • 36 months • 54 months

with a series of choice tasks, each comprising three choice objects described by randomized levels of five attributes (see Table 2). Respondents were instructed to indicate the option their organisation would most likely opt for, assuming the former were real-life options. Alternatively, they could choose a “none” option if none of the choice objects disclosed in the choice tasks were sufficiently attractive. The use of a none option is generally recommended as it more accurately reflects real-life decision situations (Hill, 2017).

Attributes and levels were selected based on the results of a preliminary study. The latter included a literature review of the factors affecting auction-participation decisions, five semi-structured interviews with onshore wind energy project developers held between November 2020 and February 2021, expert consultations, and prior research conducted in the context of the EU-funded AURES II and MISTRAL-ITN projects.⁷ Interviewees were provided with a list of potential attributes and asked to rank them according to their relative importance in relation to deciding whether to participate in auctions. The outcomes of this pre-study led to the identification of five auction attributes (see Table 2). The attributes and levels were designed to reflect the risk exposure various types of bidders face when participating in auctions, and to echo the policy trends described in Subsection 2.2. A symmetrical design was used to avoid the number-of-levels effect (Salm et al., 2016) – i.e., when attributes with more levels are associated with higher importance scores than those with fewer levels.

The gross internal rate of return (‘Gross IRR’) attribute provided an indication of the annual return project developers could expect to make on their investment if their bid was successful in the auction and support was awarded. The Gross IRR included three levels – namely, 4%, 7%, and 10%. This design was chosen to elicit the broad range of returns respondents may require to be willing to accept changes in other attribute levels. The ‘financial pre-qualification’ attribute represented the financial guarantee the auctioneer required for project developers to participate in the auction, and included three levels – namely, 5,000 €/MW, 30,000 €/MW, and 70,000 €/MW. These levels were selected to approximate minimum and maximum ranges defined in existing national regulations based on the AURES II database of EU renewable energy auctions,⁸ and to elicit a broad range of preferences.

The ‘mandatory share offer to local residents’ attribute corresponded to the obligation of developers to offer all citizens whose permanent address is within a 5 km radius of the hypothetical onshore wind energy project the opportunity to invest equity capital and own a minimum share of the project, with voting rights. Three attribute levels were

⁷ <http://aures2project.eu/>; <https://mistral-itn.eu/>. In particular, the AURES II online database of RE auctions in the EU (See: <http://aures2project.eu/auction-database/>; Status as of 30.04.2021).

⁸ <http://aures2project.eu/auction-database/>.

selected – namely, 0%, 10%, and 20%. Fig. A2 in appendix illustrates the capital structure of the hypothetical project that included the share offer to local citizens. In addition, complementary information about the conditions of the share offer was provided to respondents.⁹

The ‘level of competition’ attribute was defined as specified in Subsection 2.1.2, and three levels were selected based on the auction outcomes presented in Subsection 2.2.4. A low level of competition referred to an auction that was expected to be 50% undersubscribed. A medium level of competition entailed an expected aggregated volume of power capacity submitted that was equal to the volume tendered in the auction. A high level of competition implied an auction that was oversubscribed by 50%. Further, the ‘realisation period’ attribute represented the amount of time respondents were granted to develop the hypothetical project after winning the auction. Attribute levels were designed to reflect the range of realisation periods observed in different European markets, and included 24, 36, and 54 months.

Finally, the questionnaire included a total of ten randomized choice tasks. Fig. 2 provides an example of a choice task as presented to respondents.

3.4. Model specification and willingness-to-accept estimation

First, we estimated the relative preferences of project developers for different auction design elements – or part-worth utilities – by specifying a two-level Hierarchical Bayes (HB) model based on survey data using the Sawtooth Software. HB models are often used in such studies as they enable to address the potential lack of information at the individual respondent level by drawing information from other respondents. This makes this approach particularly relevant when the number of total observations is limited (Rao, 2014). At the lower level (individual respondent level), respondents are assumed to systematically select their preferred auction participation options based on their respective aggregated part-worth utilities. A multinomial logit model is used to specify the choice probability of individuals. At the upper level (across the population of respondents), a multivariate normal distribution comprising a means vector and covariances matrix is used to estimate the variation of individual part-worth utilities between respondents and to indicate the level of heterogeneity in the sample (Allenby et al., 2005;

⁹ Respondents were informed that the share offer consisted of notifying all eligible parties in writing through at least one advertisement in a local newspaper, and a mandatory public hearing. Respondents were told that the share offer had to take place no earlier than two months before the planned commissioning of the first wind turbine. They were informed that if not all shares were subscribed to, their organisation could keep those that remained outstanding. Finally, respondents were told that failure to comply with regulations would result in loss of support.

Gross Internal Rate of Return (IRR)	4%	7%	10%	My organisation would not be interested in any of these options.
Financial pre-qualification	5 000 €/MW	5 000 €/MW	5 000 €/MW	
Mandatory share offer to local residents	10%	20%	0%	
Level of competition	Medium level of competition	High level of competition	Low level of competition	
Realisation period	54 months	36 months	24 months	

Fig. 2. Example of choice task used in the choice experiment.
Source: Authors' elaboration generated with Sawtooth Software's module SSI Web.

Orme and Howell, 2009).

The root likelihood (RLH) parameter is used to provide an indication of the quality of the HB model (Orme, 2016). A high RLH value denotes a good fit between the model and data, with $RLH = 1$ indicating the best fit. In this study, the HB model is associated with an average $RLH = 0.72$.¹⁰ Given that respondents were presented with three auction participation options and one opt-out option per choice task, the null likelihood corresponds to $1/4 = 0.25$ (Sawtooth Software, 2021). Since the RLH value associated with the HB model is 2.88 times greater than the null likelihood value, the model is assumed to adequately fit the dataset (Hille et al., 2018).

Second, using part-worth utility results we computed aggregated willingness-to-accept (WTA) values following Salm and Wüstenhagen (2018). This allowed us to estimate the risk premium bidders would require to be willing to participate in auctions that include less preferred design elements. Results of the HB analysis can be found in Subsection 4.2, and WTA estimates in Subsection 4.3 and 4.4.

3.5. Data collection and sample

We identified potential respondents using a database that included 2,514 wind energy development companies,¹¹ contact lists, web searches, and relevant associations. We contacted a total of 370 potential respondents individually via email or direct messaging through a social media platform (LinkedIn) between April and June 2021. An initial message including information about the research project, data usage, and confidentiality was first sent out. A reminder was also sent in most cases, except when direct messaging via social media was used (as LinkedIn does not allow users to send multiple messages unless the initial one is accepted by recipients). Additionally, respondents were recruited through seven European and national RE associations that disseminated the survey among their members.¹² Survey responses were

collected between April and July 2021.

One hundred and eighty-five respondents accessed the survey. After excluding incomplete responses, nine respondents who completed the survey but did not correspond to the target population were also removed from the sample. Insights from a total of 61 project developers who made an aggregated 559 experimental decisions are thus included in the final sample, corresponding to a response rate of 16.5%.¹³ Respondents took on average 18 min to complete the survey. The final sample contains seven partial survey responses where sufficient information was provided to permit their inclusion in the analysis. The sample size is limited by the small population of European onshore wind project development companies. Nevertheless, it is aligned with the sample size used in similar studies with professional investors (Lüthi and Wüstenhagen, 2012; Salm, 2018) and complies with recommendations from Orme (1998) regarding sample size requirements in choice experiments.

The final sample mainly consisted of men, on average in their mid-forties. This reflects the general under-representation of other gender identities in the RE sector (IRENA, 2019). Most project developers reported having at least 10 years of work experience. Further, 52% of respondents indicated that they worked for commercial project developers, and 30% for utility companies. Respondents affiliated with energy cooperatives represent 11% of the final sample. The sample includes representatives from 31 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) – i.e., companies with up to 249 employees –, and 23 large companies. Finally, 56% of respondents reported being based in Germany or France, two of the largest European onshore wind markets. Additional information on socio-demographic data can be found in Table A1 in the appendix.

4. Results and discussion

We first present descriptive results about respondents' prior RE investment experience, factors determining decisions to engage in RE auctions, and their preferred means to support citizen participation. This allows us to gain a better understanding of the investment process in the context of auctions. Based on the results of the choice experiment, we then present part-worth utility estimates and discuss the preferences of project developers for different auction design elements. Building on these findings, we finally present willingness-to-accept estimates for all project developers and explore differences between subgroups. This allows us to shed light on how and to what extent different auction design elements, particularly those aimed at increasing citizen participation, influence risk perceptions.

¹³ Based on 370 potential respondents who were contacted via direct messaging (excluding large disseminators).

¹⁰ The mean of all respondents' individual RLH values.

¹¹ The database included 2,514 global wind energy development companies (status as of April 2021). Companies only active in the offshore wind energy sector or based outside the EU were excluded. Onshore wind energy companies that had developed (or had in development) more than five projects were selected for direct messaging (336 firms). Potential respondents were identified using personal networks, LinkedIn, and web searches. When no contact details could be found, or when project companies could be linked to other larger developers, the respective companies were excluded. The database can be found at: https://www.thewindpower.net/store_actor_en.php?id_type=1.

¹² Large disseminators include four regional and national wind or RE associations who contacted a total of 427 members mainly via mailing lists, two citizen-led RE organisations who contacted 115 members via mailing lists and LinkedIn, and Strommarkttreffen.org, which has c. 5,000 members. Since not all members corresponded to our target group, the specific number of potential respondents reached through these disseminators is unknown. Large disseminators were thus excluded from the response rate calculations, as per Melliger and Lilliestam (2021).

4.1. Descriptive results

The responses indicate that a considerable share of surveyed project developers (80%) had already participated in at least one auction round (see Fig. A3 in appendix), of which 94% reported winning at least one auction, underlining the quality of our sample. While 63% of these respondents reported having prior experience with onshore wind energy auctions, 47% revealed having prior auction experience in Germany, and 45% in France (see Fig. A4 and Fig. A5 in appendix). Interestingly, a large share of these respondents (49%) also claimed to have previously submitted bids that included, or pledged to include, citizen participation through equity or debt co-investment. Overall, 26% of respondents reported having experience with citizen co-investment as a general practice, 54% occasionally, and 20% reported no experience ($N = 54$). Specifically, 37% of respondents indicated that their organisation tends to offer investment opportunities of between 1% and 10% of the overall project value, and 19% of respondents between 11% and 20% (see Fig. A6 in appendix). Finally, a minority of respondents (7%) indicated offering 51% of the project value or more.

Regarding factors shaping auction participation decisions, 23% of respondents ranked the type of remuneration scheme as the most important factor, while 20% ranked the pricing rule as the second most important factor (see Fig. 3).¹⁴ These results confirm earlier findings regarding the relative importance of price risk for RE investment (Egli, 2020).¹⁵

Moreover, the preferred means of promoting citizen participation in projects subject to auction-allocated support appear to differ depending on developers' size. While two equivalent shares of SME respondents (each 19%) revealed that preferential conditions and a mandatory share offer to local residents were their preferred means of supporting citizen participation in auctions, 22% of large developers highlighted fiscal incentives as their favoured measure (see Fig. 4). These insights suggest that SMEs tend to be more inclined to favour measures directly associated with auction schemes, while large project developers prefer indirect measures outside of auction settings. As mentioned in Subsection 2.1, SMEs may face greater barriers to auction participation than larger actors. The introduction of actor diversity measures may provide them with a competitive advantage over larger companies as they are likely to have stronger ties with local communities, facilitating thus the successful realisation of citizen participation initiatives.

Regarding citizen participation in RE projects in general (not specifically in the context of auctions), most respondents reported being open to some form of citizen participation, with a considerable share preferring financial participation through equity and/or debt investment (see Fig. 5). Interestingly, both SMEs and large project developers revealed that public information events and financial participation through citizen equity investment were their preferred forms of citizen participation in RE projects. This insight is somewhat surprising since shared ownership is often associated with additional risk and costs for developers. Nevertheless, these results show that both SMEs and large project developers seem to be generally open to shared ownership.

4.2. Preferences for auction design elements

Part-worth utilities were estimated using the HB model as specified in Subsection 3.4 and zero-centred to facilitate within-attribute comparison. Table 3 presents the average zero-centred part-worth utility estimates, lower and upper 95% confidence intervals, and standard

¹⁴ We excluded the remuneration scheme and pricing rule from the choice experiment as these attributes are less relevant to our core research focus, namely measures to support citizen participation and actor diversity.

¹⁵ This may be explained by the fact that specific pricing rules may incentivize strategic or low bidding (Polzin et al., 2019), resulting in additional uncertainty regarding the level of support developers may receive.

deviation (SD) values.

As expected, part-worth utility estimates show that respondents tend to prefer higher Gross IRR values (see Table 3). Regarding financial pre-qualifications, project developers appear to prefer a smaller financial guarantee. This insight supports the findings of prior studies that highlight the additional risk stringent guarantee requirements may generate for RE investors (Grashof, 2019). Indeed, we informed survey respondents that the auctioneer would keep the financial guarantee if the hypothetical project was not realized. Correspondingly, larger guarantees have the potential to become translated into higher penalties.

As for the mandatory share offer to local residents, results show that respondents tend to prefer no share offer requirement in the context of auctions. While this finding corroborates the overall preference of large developers for citizen participation measures operating outside the scope of auction schemes, these results are inconclusive with respect to SME responses, as this actor group overall prefers within-auction measures (see Subsection 4.1). The relatively high SD estimates associated with these attribute levels indicate considerable variation among respondents (see Table 3). Additional HB analyses conducted separately with SMEs and large developers reveal that both actor groups have overall similar preferences with regard to the mandatory share offer attribute (see Table A2 in appendix). However, the preferences of SMEs for different share offer levels vary considerably. Examination of individual-level preferences shows that all SMEs respondents who reported being affiliated with RE cooperatives preferred a 20% mandatory share offer. Despite other SME respondents also being inclined to favour some form of share offer, most exhibited strong preferences for no mandatory offer, indicating preference heterogeneity within this group.

As for the level of competition, results show the overall preference for a low level of competition as opposed to a medium or high level. As mentioned in Subsection 2.1, higher levels of competition increase allocation risk and reduce the probability of being awarded support. However, low levels of competition may increase bid prices and result in high costs for energy consumers and taxpayers. Regarding the realisation period, respondents tend to prefer 36 months compared to 24 months or 54 months. A 36-month realisation period is typical in onshore wind auction designs across Europe, potentially explaining why respondents generally tend to prefer this timeframe. As explained in Subsection 2.1.4, a shorter realisation period may increase the perceived risk of incurring penalties if a project is delayed or not realized, and a longer period may be perceived as an opportunity for speculative behaviour.

Finally, an opt-out option was included for respondents to select when they judged that none of the choice alternatives were sufficiently attractive. The total share of choice tasks in relation to which respondents did not choose any of the auction-participation concepts (i.e., opted out) is 19.9% ($N = 61$). Interestingly, large project developers chose to not participate in any auctions in only 11.3% of cases, while SMEs chose to opt-out in 25.8% of cases. This insight supports studies which suggest that smaller actors tend to face greater barriers to auction participation than larger ones (Grashof, 2019; Gsänger and Karl, 2020; Tews, 2018).

4.3. Willingness to accept

We computed aggregated WTA values to estimate the risk premiums respondents would require to be willing to participate in auctions that include less preferred design elements. Fig. 6 shows the WTA results for all project developers. A WTA of zero indicates the most preferred attribute level. A positive WTA value represents the average additional risk premium respondents would require to participate in an auction that includes a less desirable design element instead of the preferred auction design, as specified in Subsection 4.2.

Results show that respondents are sensitive to the risk associated with financial pre-qualification, with the required risk premium increasing exponentially with higher bid bond levels. While moving

Fig. 3. Factors with the greatest influence on the decision of project developers to participate in renewable energy auctions (one answer per factor possible, N = 61).

Fig. 4. Preferred means of promoting citizen participation in projects subject to auction-allocated financial support (one answer possible, N = 54).

from a bid bond valued at 5'000 €/MW to 30'000 €/MW is acceptable in exchange for an additional return of 0.43 percentage points, respondents are only willing to accept the highest level of this attribute (70'000 €/MW) for a premium of 1.79 percentage points (see Fig. 6). These results show that respondents generally appear to be willing to participate in auctions for which a financial pre-qualification is required up to a certain threshold. The former also indicate the reluctance of most project developers to take on any allocation risk unless they are compensated for it, supporting the findings of studies which show that this risk is perceived by bidders as being one of the most important ones associated with auctions (Dukan and Kitzing, 2021).

As for the level of competition, the surveyed investors unsurprisingly prefer lower to higher levels of competition, and are only willing to

participate in an oversubscribed auction in exchange for a risk premium of 1.75 percentage points.

When it comes to the realisation period, the picture that emerges is less clear. The preferred period is 36 months. Compared to this, a longer period of 54 months is the second-most preferred option, whereas the least preferred option is the shortest period included in our experiment. To move from 36 to only 24 months respondents require a risk premium of 1.67 percentage points. The non-linear distribution of part-worth utilities for this attribute illustrates that the professional investors in our sample have a shared understanding of the realistic timeline required from winning an auction to actually implementing a project. Speeding up this process may induce additional challenges, such as being under pressure to finalize negotiations with suppliers or address

Fig. 5. Preferred means of citizen participation in renewable energy projects (two answers possible, N = 54).

Fig. 6. Willingness to accept results for all project developers (N = 61).

potential social acceptance issues. At the other end of the spectrum, an extended timeline is also perceived as creating additional risks for developers. This could be related to attracting participants who have not properly planned their projects, or because throughout the development process complications may arise in relation to suppliers and other key stakeholders. This was also underlined by several of our pre-study interviewees.

Finally, regarding the attribute mandatory share offer to local residents, our findings show that while project developers may see value in citizen co-investment in general (see Subsection 4.1), they are also clearly aware of the risks involved. Accordingly, the risk premium increases almost linearly with the share of capital that needs to be offered. To move from no required participation to offering one-fifth of capital to local residents, respondents would ask for a risk premium of 1.30 percentage points.

4.4. Differences in willingness to accept between large and small project developers

In the final step, we conducted a segmentation analysis to explore differences in willingness to accept between different investor types. For this, we split the sample by firm size, calculating WTA separately for respondents working for large developers and SMEs (see Subsection 3.5 for information on subgrouping). Results are presented in Fig. 7.

We find that, apart from the level of competition where few differences between SMEs and large developers are observed, some interesting nuances emerge in relation to the other attributes. When it comes to financial pre-qualification, SMEs are more sensitive to high levels of this attribute than large developers. This situation may be driven by two factors: On the one hand, 70'000 €/MW represents a more significant amount of money for a small organisation than a large organisation, potentially representing a greater barrier to auction participation. On the other hand, large developers may be better able to diversify the risk

Table 3

Results of the HB model for all project developers: Zero-centred utilities, lower and upper 95% confidence interval, and standard deviations (N = 61).

Attribute	Attribute levels	Zero-centred utilities	Lower and upper 95% confidence interval	Standard deviations
Gross IRR	4%	-101.55	[-110.43; -92.66]	35.40
	7%	22.41	[16.35; 28.47]	24.15
	10%	79.14	[67.35; 90.92]	46.97
Financial pre-qualification	5 000 €/MW	23.18	[16.86; 29.50]	25.20
	30 000 €/MW	9.74	[5.42; 14.06]	17.23
	70 000 €/MW	-32.92	[-40.88; -24.96]	31.71
Mandatory share offer to local residents	0%	20.15	[9.36; 30.94]	42.99
	10%	0.34	[-4.83; 5.51]	20.60
	20%	-20.48	[-33.48; -7.49]	51.79
Level of competition	Low level of competition	21.23	[14.39; 28.06]	27.24
	Medium level of competition	12.29	[7.05; 17.53]	20.87
	High level of competition	-33.52	[-39.38; -27.66]	23.35
Realisation period	24 months	-29.89	[-36.01; -23.78]	24.37
	36 months	22.50	[17.40; 27.60]	20.32
	54 months	7.39	[-0.75; 15.54]	32.45
None-option	N/A	-1.08	[-30.29; 28.14]	116.43

of losing a bid bond by pursuing a larger portfolio of projects, as suggested in Subsection 2.1.1.

With regard to the realisation period, SMEs follow the pattern described in Subsection 4.3, preferring 36 months over both shorter and longer timelines. While large developers are almost indifferent in terms of the choice between 36 and 54 months, they are more sensitive to shorter implementation periods than SMEs. This may reflect the fact that smaller developers tend to be more agile, whereas respondents working in large firms are painfully aware of the challenges involved in speeding up processes within their organisations (Hockerts and Wüstenhagen, 2010). As such, they may be cognizant of the fact that they have less of a relative advantage over their smaller competitors in settings when moving swiftly is required.

The largest difference between both groups occurs with regard to the attribute mandatory share offer to citizens, where it is again the larger firms that are about twice as risk averse as their smaller competitors. Interestingly, that difference is even more pronounced at the medium level of this attribute. Offering 10% of capital to local residents is something that SMEs tend to be relatively comfortable with, possibly reflecting their greater ability to interact with local stakeholders.

5. Conclusions and policy implications

This study investigated how the design of renewable energy (RE) auctions influences the risk perceptions of project developers. Auctions were initially introduced with a focus on lowering the cost of RE policy support, but decision-makers are increasingly aware that effective policies involve meeting a broader set of objectives, including increasing actor diversity and social acceptance. The introduction of auction design elements intended to achieve those objectives has led to mixed results. Our study generates novel and fine-grained empirical insights about developers' perceptions of those auction design elements and the implications for their assessment of risk-adjusted returns.

Based on 559 experimental investment choices made by 61 European onshore wind energy developers, we find that professional investors are sensitive to a number of risks embedded in auction designs, and that they are only willing to accept an increase in the level of those risks when remuneration from the auction represents sufficient compensation. Our findings serve as a reminder that, in some respects, the interests of project developers and policymakers are in clear contrast to each other. For example, while policymakers seek to minimize cost and increase competition, project developers prefer projects with greater profitability along with predictable and stable returns, and tend to be less willing to accept auction settings that involve high levels of

Fig. 7. Differentiated willingness-to-accept results for SMEs and large project developers (N = 54).

competition. An average risk premium of 1.75 percentage points would be required by developers to participate in an oversubscribed auction instead of an undersubscribed one.

While policymakers cannot simply design auctions based on maximizing the utility of RE investors, there are certain design elements in relation to which taking the experience of developers into account may be desirable. For example, when it comes to the required implementation period of projects winning an auction, our survey respondents on average preferred a period of 36 months and tended to be sensitive to the risks involved with both shorter and longer time horizons. Therefore, well-meaning policymakers who think longer project realisation periods will encourage investor diversity should be mindful that this only works to an extent, as very long realisation periods are perceived to increase rather than decrease risk. We also found differences between investor types: SMEs would require an average risk premium of 0.97 percentage points to move from an auction with a 36-month realisation period to one with 54 months. In contrast, project developers, especially larger ones, would also require a considerable risk premium to accept a shorter realisation period. A mid-range design is thus overall preferred. One area where actor diversity may benefit from policy differentiation is financial pre-qualification. Our results show that project developers are generally willing to accept the requirement to submit a bid bond up to a certain threshold, with smaller players reacting more sensitively than larger ones. This provides empirical support for policymakers who have decided to offer preferential conditions to smaller actors in relation to this particular design element.

As for auction design elements that facilitate citizen co-investment, our results shows that while developers may be generally open to co-investment, they are also clearly aware of the risks implied by it. The required risk premium increases with the share of capital that needs to be offered to local residents. Offering 20% of capital to residents implies a risk premium of 1.3 percentage points for the overall sample, and this premium is about twice as large among large developers than for SMEs. In general, the value of citizen co-investment, especially at medium levels (such as 10% of capital offered to local residents), seems to be more appreciated among SMEs than larger players, possibly because of their superior ability to interact with local stakeholders.

Based on these insights, three policy implications become clear. First, since moderate financial pre-qualifications do not appear to significantly increase risk premiums, policymakers may want to promote their use in auction settings to ensure timely project realisation. Second, shorter realisation periods are one of the factors driving the largest increase in implied risk premiums, especially for larger project developers. This may reflect the current acceptance and permitting issues observed in many major European markets. By adapting permitting regimes through institutional capacity building and creating “one-stop shops”, national permitting authorities could shorten realisation periods and reduce risk premiums – a proposition already highlighted by some industry stakeholders to accelerate the energy transition (Richard, 2021; WindEurope, 2020). Third, our results serve as a reminder that auctions are not a panacea for delivering on a broad variety of policy objectives beyond cost effectiveness, and that promoting actor diversity in this context comes at a price. While our study has highlighted important nuances that may help improve current auction designs, auctions are not a one-size-fits-all solution to the multiple objectives pursued by energy policies. In particular, the results of this study point towards the apparent trade-off between building in elements that maximize citizen co-investment on one hand, and creating low-cost projects on the other. Policymakers unwilling to compensate project developers for the risks and complexities associated with involving local residents through financial participation will either have to find other ways to promote

actor diversity and social acceptance, or may be faced with failure to achieve their RE policy objectives. In this respect, policymakers could consider introducing more ample exemptions from auction participation for community-based and/or citizen-driven business models.

This study has limitations that pave the way for future research. While design elements aimed at encouraging citizen participation in RE projects may increase social acceptance, further research is needed to better understand the threshold at which improvements in local community acceptance are outweighed by decreases in cost effectiveness in auction settings. This could contribute to a more refined understanding of the trade-offs that policymakers will have to acknowledge when assessing the suitability of auctions for achieving a multitude of policy objectives, including fostering actor diversity and local acceptance. This study provides exploratory evidence of how different auction designs influence risk perceptions. Future research could build on these findings using qualitative methods such as focus groups to further explore developers' attitudes and perceptions, particularly regarding the shared ownership risk. It could also investigate the effect of increasing levels of competition on citizen participation, including in the context of a mandatory share offer. Once sufficient data on citizen participation in the context of auctions become available, our stated preference analysis could be complemented with revealed preference methods. Finally, future research could explore the impact of other actor diversity measures on the risk perceptions of bidders (e.g., multi-criteria auctions).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Elizabeth Côté: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Mak Dukan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Cristian Pons-Seres de Brauwer:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Rolf Wüstenhagen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Table A1
Socio-demographic results.

Variable	Value	%
Gender identity (N = 54)	Women	11%
	Men	80%
	Non-binary	2%
	Rather not say	7%
Age (N = 54)	Average	43
	Less than 5 years	7%
Work experience (N = 54)	5–9 years	17%
	10–14 years	24%
	15–19 years	24%
	20–25 years	7%
	More than 25 years	20%
Industry specification (N = 61)	Multinational utility company	28%
	Local/regional utility company	2%
	Multinational commercial project developer	31%
	Local/regional commercial project developer	21%
	Energy cooperative	11%
	Other	7%
Company size (N = 54)	1 to 9	24%
	10 to 49	13%
	50 to 249	20%
	250 and more	43%
Working country (N = 54)	Austria	4%
	Belgium	7%
	Croatia	7%
	Denmark	7%
	France	17%
	Germany	39%
	Italy	4%
	Spain	2%
	Switzerland	4%
	United Kingdom	4%
Others	6%	

Introduction

In the upcoming section, you will be asked to choose from different **options to participate in a wind energy auction**. These options are based on several characteristics shown in the table below. Please read the following explanations carefully to fully understand the characteristics used in the upcoming interactive section.

Imagine you want to participate in an **auction hosted by a European country** with a robust credit rating (AA or higher) and comprehensive regulatory framework, **to obtain support for an onshore wind project (i.e. 15 MW installed capacity, 30% capacity factor)**. Characteristics of the auction are:

- **Technology-specific** (onshore wind only)
- **'Pay-as-bid'** (awarded bidders are paid the bid price they submit)
- **Two-sided contract-for-difference for 20 years** (you must return the upside when the electricity price is above the bid level, and receive support when it is below)
- **Building permit required**
- The same rules apply to **all bidders**.

Please read the explanations below carefully to understand the categories used in the following interactive section. You can re-visit these definitions at any time in the upcoming section by scrolling your pointer over each category.

Fig. A1. Introductory text of the choice experiment with description of the hypothetical auction scheme and project characteristics (Note: the table referred to in this text corresponds to [Table 2](#)).

Source: Authors' elaboration generated with Sawtooth Software's module SSI Web.

Fig. A2. Example of capital structure associated with the mandatory share offer to local residents attribute, as disclosed to survey respondents.

Fig. A3. Previous experience of project developers with participation in renewable energy auctions and the inclusion of citizen investment (N = 61).

Fig. A4. Types of renewable energy auction project developers had previously participated in (multiple answers possible, N = 49).

Fig. A5. Countries in which project developers had previously participated in renewable energy auctions (multiple answers possible, N = 49).

Fig. A6. Typical share of project ownership or revenue developers offer to citizens (one answer possible, N = 54).

Table A2

Results of the HB model for SMEs and large developers: Zero-centred utilities, lower and upper 95% confidence interval, and standard deviations (N = 54).

Attribute	Attribute levels	HB model small and medium-sized enterprises (N = 31)			HB model large project developers (N = 23)		
		Zero-centred utilities	Lower and upper 95% CI	Standard deviations	Zero-centred utilities	Lower and upper 95% CI	Standard deviations
Gross IRR	4%	-97.74	[-110.90; -84.58]	37.37	-97.76	[-108.43; -87.08]	26.13
	7%	18.06	[9.01; 27.11]	25.71	19.18	[9.62; 28.74]	23.40
	10%	79.68	[61.36; 98.01]	52.05	78.58	[63.89; 93.27]	35.94
Financial pre-qualification	5 000 €/MW	26.73	[18.76; 34.71]	22.67	22.01	[9.20; 34.82]	31.34
	30 000 €/MW	10.16	[5.40; 14.91]	13.51	3.39	[-6.69; 13.46]	24.66
	70 000 €/MW	-36.89	[-46.72; -27.07]	27.92	-25.40	[-41.60; -9.19]	39.64
Mandatory share offer to local residents	0%	11.79	[-4.43; 28.01]	46.08	31.46	[19.96; 42.95]	28.12
	10%	3.69	[-2.72; 10.10]	18.21	-5.19	[-16.28; 5.91]	27.16
	20%	-15.48	[-34.93; 3.96]	55.23	-26.27	[-40.91; -11.64]	35.81
Level of competition	Low level of competition	19.42	[7.79; 31.06]	33.05	20.71	[10.97; 30.45]	23.83
	Medium level of competition	12.93	[7.37; 18.48]	15.79	12.17	[0.46; 23.89]	28.66
	High level of competition	-32.35	[-44.69; -20.01]	35.05	-32.88	[-40.82; -24.95]	19.42
Realisation period	24 months	-20.92	[-31.70; -10.13]	30.63	-45.95	[-51.45; -40.46]	13.45
	36 months	24.77	[17.27; 32.27]	21.30	22.15	[11.68; 32.63]	25.63
	54 months	-3.85	[-14.77; 7.06]	31.00	23.80	[12.04; 35.57]	28.79

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